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The challenges of open networks: a report on the development of a graph database for performing arts

This article gives a brief insight into the ongoing process of merging multiple legacy databases at the Swiss Archive of the Performing Arts towards one unified graph database. In its second part it raises questions in regard to whether the technical shift from relational to graph databases also can be understood as a cultural shift, which enables new forms of data-driven narratives.

Keywords: archival data, database, ontology, knowledge graph, linked data.

The Swiss Archive of the Performing Arts and its database (s)

Only even three years in existence, the Swiss Archive of the Performing Arts must be called a young institution. But SAPA emerged from three original institutions with distinct histories and also with different mind sets. The first initiative to preserve, represent, and research Swiss theater culture goes back to the late 1920s. However, it then needed half a century until the Swiss Theatre Collection, the oldest of SAPA's predecessors, was founded in 1978. It was characterized by its claim to document national theater culture in a broad sense; later it became a research facilitator due to its close connections with the Institute of Theater Studies at the University of Bern; and it also created a small museum to present theater culture to the general public.¹ Our branch in the French-speaking part of Switzerland, in Lausanne, started as the Swiss Dance Archive in the early 1990s, not only with a focus on dance but also as a community driven approach that collected material in a more focused way. The former Dance Media Library in Zurich, finally, emerged from a media practice, that is the fact that choreographers and dancers had started to record their rehearsals and performances and that this entailed a need to make their recordings available to others and to preserve them. The archives in Lausanne and Zurich merged in 2011 and in 2017 were joined by the Theatre Collection in Bern.

We have kept our three facilities in Bern, Lausanne and Zurich and are working on integrating our manifold collections, our individual cultures, and our different databases. The planned database will play a crucial role in this process as it will make the accessible the varied holdings and reveal their connections that at the moment are not easy to track as the distinct solutions have created equally distinct orders and identifications of entities. The first legacy database that we want to supersede here is scopeArchiv, a professional, proprietary archival software, which is in use in Lausanne and in Zurich. ScopeArchiv organizes information on the collection hierarchically according to provenance and the ISAD (G) standard.² But in doing so it is agnostic towards the peculiarities of the holdings and what distinguishes performing arts from other fields. In Bern, the main database software is FileMaker Pro, which has the advantage of being very flexible as users can easily create new fields to represent domain knowledge. The result, however, is that we don't have one but many specialized databases for all kinds of information. Each of these captures a subfield of performing arts, like a small collection of masks, but is unrelated to the other databases and not based on general standards. We also have spreadsheets which are even easier to create and then often grow in uncontrollable ways. There are also a lot of physical documents, orderly shelved but not documented in any database. Finally, there are humans who know how to connect all these bits of information but for various reasons are not the best data storage solution for archives.

In order to find out what kind of database we want to have, we conducted a series of staff workshops and discussed our objectives and what our users would need. The result was a one-page paper with the idea of «Multiple Perspectives on Performing Arts» that sketches out a non-technical vision of our future database.

So, our main objectives herein are:

- to document people, institutions, and productions with respect to the complexity and ephemerality of the field
- to provide access for users coming from distinct backgrounds
- to offer incremental search to facilitate unexpected findings
- to allow different perspectives on the holdings
- to give users the possibility to take their findings with them
- finally, we decided that we are interested in sharing our solution with other archives³

Parallel to this and with support by the Bern University of Applied Sciences we developed a comprehensive but abstract data model that can represent the information contained in our legacy databases and enables us to further increase the quality of the data.⁴ The «Data Model for the Swiss Performing Arts Platform» (SPA) data model is based on three ontologies, which we had to combine for our specific needs. The standards we used are CIDOC–CRM — developed by ICOM for the museum sector —, FRBRoo — its extension for libraries — and Records in Contexts (RiC) — a new archival standard proposed by ICA, which is supposed to supplement ISAD (G) in the near future. Herein, CIDOC–CRM facilitates us to represent general concepts such as persons, places, and times in a widely accepted form. FRBRoo has the function to make the specific trajectories of works of performing arts as ephemeral and based on other works traceable.⁵ RiC is a way to preserve provenance information while at the same time

¹ Regarding the history of the Swiss Theatre Collection see Susanna Tschui, «Schweizerische Theatersammlung, Bern BE», in *Theaterlexikon der Schweiz* (Zürich: Chronos, 2005), http://tls.theaterwissenschaft.ch/wiki/Schweizerische_Theatersammlung,_Bern_BE; *Mimos: Zeitschrift der Schweizerischen Gesellschaft für Theaterkultur*, nos. 3–4, Themenheft zur Schweizerischen Theatersammlung (2009).

² *The General International Standard Archival Description* defines rules and specific elements that should be used for describing archival holdings. It was approved and published by the International Council on Archives (ICA) in its second edition in 2000.

³ Foundation SAPA, «*Vision Swiss Performing Arts Platform*», September 13, 2017, <http://datahub.io/dataset/spa-data>

⁴ Beat Estermann and Christian Schneeberger, «Data Model for the Swiss Performing Arts Platform», draft version 0.51, 2017, <https://datahub.io/dataset/spa-data>.

⁵ For further details on how this can be done with FRBRoo see Martin Doerr, Patrick Le Boeuf, and Chryssoula Bekiari, «FRBRoo, a Conceptual Model for Performing Arts», in *2008 Annual Conference of CIDOC, Athens, 2008*, 15–18.

disrupting its strong hierarchical order. We are currently in the process of implementing the data model into a more concrete specification, which is based on actual data.⁶

Database operations and narrations

In the second part of my paper, I would like to address some conceptual issues in regard to databases that we have encountered in this process. Databases are usually seen as technical solutions for storing information in various ways. Such a static conception of databases can be confronted with an operational perspective as the Swiss historian of technology David Gugerli has done in his cultural history of search engines.⁷ Search engines — and Gugerli has a very broad understanding of what that is — are our primary mode of interacting with databases. Gugerli's history of the search engine starts with the German version of the American quiz show «What's my line?», in which a fixed team of four persons is trying to identify the often obscure professions of ordinary people by asking them simple yes-or-no-questions. Looking back on the show today with its monotonous rituals, it is difficult not to think of watching an algorithm at work just at a time when computers were something that most people had heard about but never seen or even used. But what made the show so successful for several decades, according to Gugerli, is its way to create narrations around a growing database of professions in an increasingly complex world. In contrast and by the example of the films of Dziga Vertov, the cultural theorist Lev Manovich has suggested that the database had potentially succeeded the narrative as a predominant cultural form.⁸ However, the example of «What's my line?» shows that databases create new kinds of narratives because narratives are a way of conceiving data as meaningful. Gugerli's approach here is relevant as he reminds us that we should not simply ask how a database can represent certain information (as I have done myself in first half of this paper) but also how we interact with it and what might be the broader cultural aspects of such operations.

As we want to enable new forms of operations with our data, information that is currently stored in regular text fields needs to be made machine-readable. This is a process of formalization of the statements contained in free textual form. As an example we can take the contents of a field for the cast of a performing arts production. Currently, this is a list of names separated either by commas or semicolons, which have to be split and individually identified. As the same name might refer to different persons, this process cannot be fully automated — not to speak of names with typos or wrong separators between them. It becomes more complicated when a name is followed by additional information in parenthesis because the ambiguity no longer only concerns the identity of what is mentioned but also its meaning in relations to the person it attributes. Such additional information might refer to the function or role a cast member has («Julia», «violin»), her origin («New York»), home institution («Staatstheater Karlsruhe»), or various other things. For a human this information is not very difficult to understand, for a computer this would require a lot of contextual knowledge. There are many more conventions to express certain meanings such as square brackets for assumptions of the archivists that are not backed by documents. So why do we try to explain our data to a computer that will likely never understand a theater performance? To create a different kind of and hopefully better search engine.⁹

The consistent identification of entities, such as persons or plays in different contexts, becomes much easier with the technical shift from relational to graph databases, sometimes referred to as knowledge graphs. Relational databases were originally conceived by Edgar F. Codd in 1970 and are simply multiple interlinked but in themselves uniform tables.¹⁰ This approach provides a simple way to combine different and similar information. We may think of a museum's inventory here. The descriptions of artworks can be uniform to a certain degree as they have common types of information like creation date, size, technique, and, of course, authorship. So one can easily put this information into a table where each row represents a specific work. But if we also want to store additional information about the artists like life dates or nationality, we would have to repeat this information with each additional work in the table. To avoid this one creates a second table containing all artists, gives them unique identifiers and in the table of artworks only refers to the identifier of the artist.

In reality one often ends up with many more tables and complexity increases while the restrictiveness of the tables itself remains. So relational databases do not seem to be the most «natural» way of describing things. As an alternative, artificial intelligence researchers in their pursuit to describe basically everything and not only limited domain knowledge came up with the idea to use simple sentences — subject, predicate, object — with strong semantics that create loose networks of statements. A well-known illustration in a white paper by the W3C shows such a network of people and works.¹¹ It defines person called Alice, Bob, and Leonard da Vinci and an artwork called «The Mona Lisa». These nodes of the network are connected with edges such as «is a friend of», «is interested in», and «was created by». The results are statement like «Bob is interested in the Mona Lisa» and if we agree on what the single elements of these statements mean, we can create further, related statements. Such a structure is much more flexible than a relational database because it is not built for a single purpose. Both, Bob and Leonardo da Vinci, might be «subject of» another work, Bob might be an artist himself, etc. This also makes a difference when it comes to searching. Where in relational databases we search for values in table cells, in a knowledge graph we can more easily search for patterns like for example «Give me a list of all persons who have visited places in France and are friends Bob.»

The replacement of ambivalent names with arbitrary but unique identifiers is a first step in structuring data to be machine-readable and linkable. One of the most relevant databases here is Wikidata, a sister project of the better-known Wikipedia, which contains structured data instead of prose texts. If we want to make statements in our database about the Bolshoi Theater, we cannot do so by using its name because its spelling is different in the four languages we use (English, German, French, and Italian). In Wikidata the Bolshoi Theater is known as Q138908,¹² an identity that comes with labels in many languages to make it useful for humans while still being unambiguous for machines. Tim Berners-Lee, the inventor of the World Wide Web, described this concept of structured

⁶ The specifications of our data can be found at <https://sapa.github.io/spa-specifications>. The database itself will be available at <https://performing-arts.ch>.

⁷ David Gugerli, *Suchmaschinen: Die Welt als Datenbank* (Frankfurt/M.: Suhrkamp, 2009).

⁸ Lev Manovich, *The Language of New Media* (Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 2001).

⁹ To give another example: In our current data, I found about a dozen different ways to refer to the Bolshoi Theater, which can partly be explained with varying and language-dependent transliterations of Cyrillic into Latin letters. The search for Bolshoi productions turns into a question of trial and error this way.

¹⁰ Edgar F. Codd, «A Relational Model of Data for Large Shared Data Banks», *Communications of the ACM* 13, no. 6 (June 1970): 377–87, doi:10.1145/362384.362685.

¹¹ «RDF 1.1 Primer: W3C Working Group Note 24 June 2014», <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf11-primer/>, fig. 1.

¹² Or to be precise <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q138908>.

data in 2006 as Linked Data and the last decade saw many Linked Data projects by cultural heritage institutions with the objective to connect their respective databases.¹³ But linking doesn't only happen between different institutions. It also needs to happen within each institution where it might even be more difficult because it often requires the shift from relational databases to graph databases. We can see this looking at the data portal of the French National Library, which brings together three internal databases to publish their data in one place as Linked Data.¹⁴ But within the merged data there are still hardly any more links than in the original databases themselves and for example there are still no connections between different editions or translations of a specific book.

But what is my point with having more and more links between entities? The identification of and the linkage between entities allows for what we called in our short programmatic paper multiperspectivity. Linked Data can also be seen as linked perspectives. From a technical point of view, one uses templates to render selected contents of a database and with relational databases there tends to be one template per table. In my museum example with two tables for artworks and artists this would mean to have one template that shows all the information about an artwork and another one that tells us about the artist and lists her or his works. It is these structures of representation that form database narrations.

If we look at the public database of the Museum of Modern Art (MoMA) in New York, we find this structure with its menu items «The Collection» and «Artists», the two perspectives of what the MoMA has collected that we already know. What is much more interesting is the perspective of «Art terms». What we find there is a list of styles like surrealism, expressionism and so on that categorize the works in the collection. This is telling because the MoMA from its beginning saw itself as an institution that promotes an orderly narrative about the history of modern art and that it could be understood as a genealogy of styles.¹⁵ What is relatively new and what the museum has put a lot of effort in is the documentation of their exhibitions with photos and lists of artworks that were part of it. However, the database does not allow to take the «perspectives» of materials, of places or of points in time.

One can see a different narrative looking at our own old scopeArchiv database. It allows full text search, searching in specific fields or for predefined keywords, and the navigation through the archive plan. It is especially the criticism of the archive plan as the predominant mode of organizing information that has led to more open concepts like Records in Context because the given hierarchy tends to support and reiterate original power structures. But once all entities in a dataset are identified and connected in a meaningful way, each of them can become the center of attention. This levels not only the relevance of famous directors and bit players with long-term engagements but it also disrupts the supposed hierarchy of humans, works, and other categories. I assume that this paradigm shift will create some confusion at first when established narrations will be undermined and contested by alternative ones. But maybe there is hardly a better field to try this out than performing arts.

¹³ Tim Berners-Lee, «Linked Data», W3C, July 27, 2006, <https://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData>.

¹⁴ <https://data.bnf.fr>; Agnès Simon et al., «Publishing Bibliographic Records on the Web of Data: Opportunities for the BnF (French National Library)», in *The Semantic Web: Semantics and Big Data*, ed. Philipp Cimiano et al. (Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer, 2013), 563–577.

¹⁵ Astrit Schmidt Burkhardt, «Shaping Modernism: Alfred Barr's Genealogy of Art», *Word & Image* 16, no. 4 (October 2000): 387–400, doi:10.1080/02666286.2000.10435694.

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«Государственный центральный театральный музей имени А.А. Бахрушина»
Союз музеев России
Российский комитет Международного совета музеев (ИКОМ России)
Государственный институт искусствознания
Российская академия художеств

Руководитель проекта: Д.В. Родионов

В подготовке электронного лонгрида участвовали:
И.В. Баканова, заместитель генерального директора
ГЦТМ им. А.А. Бахрушина по научной работе,
М.А. Назаретян, заведующая отделом редакционной деятельности
ГЦТМ им. А.А. Бахрушина

Составители сборника:

Т.Т. Бурлакова, заведующая научно-методическим отделом ГЦТМ им. А.А. Бахрушина,
Ю.В. Доманский, старший научный сотрудник научно-методического
отдела ГЦТМ им. А.А. Бахрушина

Литературные редакторы: И.Л. Алпатова, М.А. Дроздова,
Н.Г. Каминская, А.В. Мартынова

Редактор аннотаций на английском языке: Д.У. Руденко

Корректор: З.А. Колеченко

Макет, вёрстка: Д.В. Кошкарёв

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